

**DEVELOPMENT OF GARDENING, FRUIT AND VEGETABLE NETWORKS IN THE
REGIONS OF THE GENERAL GOVERNORATE OF TURKESTAN****School 255, Yashnabad district, Tashkent city****History teacher****Khudoynazarova Azizakhan Mirzaakbarovna**

Annotation: This article devoted to open the theme development of gardening, fruit and vegetable networks in the regions of the general governorate of Turkestan. Moreover, information about land and water reform in Turkestan were noted.

Key words: *Russian conquest, culminating, agrarian policy, resettlement of Russian, "irrigation", annual collections, capitation, endowments.*

Russian Turkestan (Russian: Русский Туркестан, romanized: Russkiy Turkestan) was the western part of Turkestan within the Russian Empire's Central Asian territories, and was administered as a Krai or Governor-Generalship. It comprised the oasis region to the south of the Kazakh Steppe, but not the protectorates of the Emirate of Bukhara and the Khanate of Khiva. It was populated by speakers of Russian, Uzbek, Kazakh, Kyrgyz, and Tajik. Although Russia had been pushing south into the steppes from Astrakhan and Orenburg since the failed Khivan expedition of Peter the Great in 1717, the beginning of the Russian conquest of Turkestan is normally dated to 1865[1]. That year the Russian forces took the city of Tashkent[1] under the leadership of General Mikhail Chernyayev expanding the territories of Turkestan Oblast (part of Orenburg Governorate-General). Chernyayev had exceeded his orders (he only had 3,000 men under his command at the time) but Saint Petersburg recognized the annexation in any case. This was swiftly followed by the conquest of Khodzhent, Dzhizak and Ura-Tyube, culminating in the annexation of Samarkand and the surrounding region on the Zeravshan River from the Emirate of Bukhara in 1868 forming the Zeravsh Special Okrug of Turkestan. An account of the Russian conquest of Tashkent was written in "Urus leshkerining Turkistanda tarikh 1262–1269 senelarda qilghan futuhlari" by Mullah Khalibay Mambetov.

In particular, according to the Minister of State Property and Agriculture AV Krivoshein, the main goals and main directions of the Russian Empire's agrarian policy which includes land and water relations in Turkestan:

“There are three views on this central issue. The first is cotton, the second is irrigation, and finally, the third, though insignificant, is, in fact, the most important thing - the resettlement of the Russians”. Thus, the emperor's minister summed up the main directions of the center's colonial policy in the country of Turkestan in three words: "cotton", "irrigation", "resettlement of Russian "[2]. The emphasis of the imperial government on the irrigation system and water resources in Turkestan at that time based on its own interests shows the topicality of the issue. The study of the irrigation system and water sources of the country of Turkestan as well as the traditions and methods of water use of the local population in the second half of the 19th century - early 20th centuries, are reflected in a number of sources and literature. Particularly, information on this topic can be found in the works of the following authors. Among them, A.I.Shakhnazarov (1908), N.N.Aleksandrov (1916), A.P.Savitsky (1963), A.M.Yuldashev (1969), A.R. Muhammadjonov (1972), Z.D. Kastelskaya (1980), Sarybaev K.S. (1995), H.E. Yunusova (2018), U.A.Usarov (2018, 2019). and works and research papers of other of authors can be included. Information on the irrigation system of the late XIX - early XX centuries can also be found in the annual collections of "Statistical materials of the country of Turkestan " in different years[3].

Precipitation and elevation shape land and water usage in Central Asia, distinguishing the southern irrigated oases from the steppes, deserts, and prairies, where instead nomadic pastoralism (sometimes rain-fed agriculture) is economically rational. The former was included in Russian Turkestan, the latter in the Steppe provinces. The colonial state recognized land usage rights of the nomads; while not formally admitting land property among the settled population, it allowed them to enjoy it within Islamic law. Nomads paid a capitation; at first tilled land continued to be taxed as a share of the real harvest. Land-assessment works from the 1890s, though, imposed a tax based on the estimated harvest value, initially on irrigated land and then, with some differences, on rain-fed land. Irrigation was paid for eminently through corvées. The increase in the share of land under cotton did not derive from state coercion but from factor endowments and absolute and relative prices. Subsidies, in the form of import duties and, above all, a growing tax break contributed to this. Despite political claims, new irrigation had a limited impact under the tsars. While the “cotton boom” altered the landscape and local economy of the oases, in the Steppe and Semirechie (now south-eastern Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan) the natives lost land to settler peasants from European Russia. The latter received land that statisticians and surveyors had deemed excess for the nomads and former nomads. Conflicts around land, water, and forests coalesced in the 1916 uprising, which in turn initiated a cycle of violent retaliation between Russians and natives that would last until the early 1920s[4]. With the establishment of

Soviet power, a first land reform “decolonized” former resettlement areas; in 1925 and 1927 another land reform aimed at reducing landlessness in southern Central Asia, while restoring pre-war output levels and cotton procurement mechanisms.

In conclusion it should be noted that after the Russian Revolution of 1917, a Turkestan Autonomous Soviet Socialist Republic (Turkestan ASSR) within the Russian Socialist Federative Soviet Republic was created in Soviet Central Asia (excluding modern-day Kazakhstan). After the foundation of the Soviet Union it was split into the Turkmen Soviet Socialist Republic (Turkmenistan) and Uzbek Soviet Socialist Republic (Uzbekistan) in 1924. The Tajik Soviet Socialist Republic (Tajikistan) was formed out of part of the Uzbek SSR in 1929, and in 1936 the Kyrgyz SSR (Kyrgyzstan) was separated from Kazakh Soviet Socialist Republic. After the collapse of the Soviet Union, these republics gained their independence.

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